

Implication of interest-bearing central bank digital currency on welfare and allocations

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ES30029 Final Year Research project

April 2024

Abstract

We explore implications of introducing an interest-bearing central bank digital currency (CBDC) on households, by comparing it against an economy with physical money only, and an economy which conducts monetary policy through commercial banks. Utilising a two-period overlapping generation model, we find introducing CBDC is pareto improving compared to an economy with physical money only, on the condition that the benefit from the higher return on money is not fully upset by the lump-sum tax required to fund the interest expense. When the pass-through between policy and deposit rate is imperfect, an economy with CBDC as the main monetary instrument will strictly dominate an economy where deposit is the only instrument. Lastly, with CBDC, policy makers allow for agents to make optimal consumption choices despite changes in inflation expectations, through retaining the true value of money; this is not feasible if agents held either deposits and/or cash in our setup.

Word count: 9999 (incl. abstract and footnotes; excl. reference, table of contents and appendix)

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1 Introduction

Central bank money, in addition to ensuring that all agents can access a safe, universally recognised common unit of account, is the core instrument which enables central bank to carry out policies. Currently, the central bank issues two types of central bank money: physical money, which is the only form of central bank money available to households, and reserve, available only to the commercial banks, and used as a means of payment between institutions. With the rapid decline in physical money, accelerated by the Covid-19 pandemic, households are in-need of a cashless form of payment instruments which is a direct claim on the central bank, rather than a liability of private financial institutions (Bank of International Settlements, BIS, 2020). Given this, most central banks around the world, are proposing for a retail central bank digital currency (CBDC). Following the taxonomy of money proposed by Bech and Garratt (2017), we characterise retail CBDC to be in the form of digital money, which is universally accessible, issued by the central bank and can be exchanged in a decentralised manner. The definition here is important. If digital currency becomes available to public without restrictions, depending on the motivations for CBDC, there are different setups we can adopt, with varying consequences. Given financial inclusion and enhancing payments remain as top motivations for central banks around the world to introduce a CBDC (BIS, 2021), most central banks opt for it to be non-interest-bearing. This setup would also allow for preservation of seigniorage, despite decline in bank notes. If central banks are forced to rely on government funding, its autonomy would be undermined, threatening both financial and price stability (Engert and Fung, 2017). With this design, CBDC will be equivalent to cash in many aspects, purposed for everyday payments and not intended for savings (Bank of England, 2023).

On the other hand, enabling CBDC to be interest-bearing has interesting policy implications. To name some briefly: firstly, if interest on CBDC is strictly positive, it would serve as a floor for deposit rates (Riksbank, 2018), making the deposit market more competitive by providing an alternative to bank deposits which households could access (Bank of Canada, 2020). Secondly, if interest on CBDC is set in accordance with other policy rates, it will become a new channel for direct policy rate pass-through to the

households, instead of relying on the banking sector, which is subject to lags and reduces efficiency of policy (Cukierman, 2020). Lastly, CBDC will enable central banks to break below the effective lower bound, such that in deflationary episodes, it could be used to stimulate economic activity. However, given the lack of empirical data, it is uncertain whether interest-bearing CBDC would shift the current financial market structure. If CBDC is a near-perfect substitute for commercial bank money, it may crowd out the aggregate amount of deposits available and in turn decrease credit availability, raising cost of financing debt for business and households (Wadsworth, 2018; Federal Reserve, 2022).

This paper contributes to the growing research on implications of granting households access to interest-bearing central bank money, by comparing three standalone economies with different means of payment: physical money, digital money/CBDC, and deposits. We focus on how an economy with CBDC would compare in terms of households' welfare, consumption choices and monetary policy efficiency in the short-run where price level is sticky. Given we do not consider risks of a run and asset available to the banking sector is restricted to reserve, households are set to be indifferent between three forms of payment. We introduce an uncompetitive banking sector, which pays a deposit rate that is discounted by an exogenous transmission parameter, such that the lower the parameter, the greater the market power of the commercial bank. Interest on deposit is funded by the interest on reserve, which equates to the rate paid on CBDC.

When inflation expectation is fixed at 2%, our model delivers the following results when compared to physical money. When $i^* = 2.6$, households receive no lump-sum transfer/tax, and their utility is maximised, such that CBDC is the only medium of exchange, and strictly dominates physical money. When $5.3\% > i > i^*$, central bank now needs to tax households to expense interest rate on digital currency. However, despite not being pareto optimal, households in CBDC economy is still strictly better-off, given the higher return on money over-compensates for the lump-sum tax needed to fund the interest expense. When $i \geq 5.3\%$, the cost of funding interest in the form of lump-sum tax, exceeds the benefit from higher return of money. Thus, in this case, holding CBDC makes households worse-off, such that it is weakly dominated by physical money.

Our model with banking sector delivers the following result. When pass-through between policy rate i and deposit rate r is perfect, described by $\mu = 1$, it makes no difference whether households in our model setup have access to CBDC or deposits. Characteristics described above when compared against physical money, are identical for CBDC and deposits. When transmission is high but imperfect, given by $\mu > 0.987$: if interest is low, described by $0 < i < 2.6\%$; despite government's expenditure on reserve is lower given reduced demand for deposit/money, the lower seigniorage revenue means households are not fully compensated in the form of lump-sum transfer. In this scenario, deposit still strictly dominates physical money given higher return of money, but is strictly dominated by CBDC. When interest is high given by $i > 2.6\%$, whilst still having to bear the cost of funding for interest on reserve, lump-sum tax on household is now lower compared to if CBDC was held instead. However, households still do not fully benefit from the higher return on money given imperfect policy pass-through. Therefore, CBDC will still strictly dominate the deposit economy if made available. Using $\mu = 0.99$ as an example, when $3.2\% \geq i > 2.6\%$, deposit weakly dominates physical money; however, once the critical threshold is exceeded ($i > 3.2\%$), deposit economy is strictly dominated by physical money, given the high tax requirement to clear government spending. When $\mu \leq 0.987$ and the central bank operates at optimal policy rate i^* , deposit is dominated by CBDC and weakly dominated by physical money, and households are made worse-off by not being able to access other means of payment. This is because despite the interest earning, net income is low given the level of lump-sum transfer received is strictly lower than if only physical money is used.

1.1 Literature

Existing literatures focuses on interest-bearing CBDC, and how it will interact with the commercial bank sector, its implication on monetary policy setting and financial stability.

Conclusions on the impact on commercial banks vary dependent on the design of CBDC and the market structure of the banking sector. When CBDC is interest-bearing and the banking sector is assumed to be non-competitive, most academics have come to the unsurprising conclusion that in order to

compete with CBDC, commercial bank will have to increase interest on saving deposits, inevitably reducing their profit (Chiu et al., 2019; Jiang and Zhu, 2019; Ryu and Webb, 2023). On the extreme, Kirkby (2018) believed that by introducing CBDC, it would eliminate the entire banking system, given the banking sector is almost entirely funded by deposits in its current form. He cautioned for the risk of having central banks responsible for all expenses relating to long-maturity assets such as credit cards, mortgage and commercial loans. However, given private banks have developed over decades of expertise in long-term asset, it is empirically sound to assume that the central bank is at a disadvantaged position to compete with the commercial bank, given they do not have access to the same investment opportunities (Fernandez-Villaverde et al., 2020). This means it is unlikely for CBDC to lead to an elimination of the banking system. Nyffenegger (2022) finds that bank lending will shrink around 3.0%-3.3% if CBDC is both a payment and saving vehicle.

An additional counterargument is made by Monnet et al. (2021), they argued that the profit of banks does not decline when CBDC is used as a mean of payment to acquire capital, given capital becomes cheaper as interest on CBDC increases. Andolfatto (2020) investigated the impact of CBDC on a monopolistic banking sector and found that CBDC will increase the supply of deposit, and even improve lending condition through higher deposit rate and lower lending rate. Wu and Chen (2021) used a four-sector DSGE model and found that whilst having an overall positive economic effect, the impact of CBDC in its use as a substitute for bank deposits is limited.

Our results align with both perspectives. Given both deposits and CBDC serve as a medium of exchange in our model, introducing CBDC increases aggregate demand for money and thus results in an expansion in the aggregate pool of money. However, given the lack of long-term assets in our setup, such that assets and liabilities of our model banking sector are respectively reserve and deposits only, CBDC will replace deposits in its entirety.

Concerning implication of monetary policy, Meaning et al. (2021) believed that a universally accessible, interest-bearing and convertible CBDC could improve efficiency of the monetary transmission mechanism. Intuitively, as CBDC increases contestability in payments, the spread between policy rate and deposit rates must lower if commercial banks want to retain depositors.

This was supported by Garratt et al. (2022), but with the negative consequence of shrinking market share of small banks. We come to similar conclusions. With CBDC replacing deposits, the spread between policy and deposit rates becoming zero, such that monetary policy rate would be directly transmitted to household, reducing policy horizon.

Academics also argued that CBDC enables negative interest rate policies. Making CBDC widely available and thus reducing the usefulness of cash, should help to breakthrough the lower bound given holding physical money is a way to avoid negative interest rates (Agarwal and Kimball, 2015; Bordo and Levin, 2017). Alternatively, if CBDC replaces cash, through levying a wallet storage fee on CBDC, making holding digital money over a certain threshold costly, the central bank could prompt consumption and inflation (Yang and Zhou, 2022).

We do see a replacement of physical money for CBDC, conditional on interest being strictly positive and not costly. Given these conditions no longer hold when interest becomes negative, our model predicts that as long as cash is accepted as a medium of exchange, households can always hold physical money to avoid the negative interest. Whether cash is phased out given lack of usage, is out of the scope of our model.

We contribute to what Carapella and Flemming (2020) believed as a crucial question for future research: CBDC as a means of payment and a store of value, how does it affect households' portfolio choices as to which monies to use. Unlike Williamson (2019), who had a similar setup where three means of payments co-circulated, we do not consider physical money to be socially costly despite its subject to theft, such that we assume households are indifferent between three types of monies. Therefore, we find when the banking sector is not competitive, CBDC is strictly preferred to deposits, but fails to eliminate physical money when interest on CBDC is over the threshold at which the cost of funding that interest for households, in the form of lump-sum tax, exceeds the benefit from higher return of money. In terms of feasible allocations, we come to the same conclusion as Williamson and see households arriving at a pareto optimal equilibrium as aggregate demand for money and output increases.

2 Benchmark model

Our benchmark model builds on the Champ, Freeman and Haslag (1994) monetary model. In what follows, I describe a simplified endowment economy as the base case for our analysis, where the central bank is the sole supplier of money.

We depart from the standard version in three ways. First, we introduce an alternative scenario which we call the CBDC case, where agents can access interest-bearing digital money. This allows us to compare a base case where physical money is the only medium of exchange, to when CBDC is also available as a means of payment. Second, we assume when the government is unable to expense interest on CBDC from seigniorage revenue alone, it must fiscally back the spending through putting a lump-sum tax on households. Such constraint will enable us to observe under what conditions it becomes optimal for households to hold physical money or/and CBDC, despite the existence of the other. Lastly, the central bank targets a constant gross rate $\pi_T > 0$, and sets monetary stances accordingly such that consumer expectations are anchored $\pi_T = \pi^e$. This will form the basis of our analysis on an efficient allocation.

2.1 Households

The model economy consists of identical individuals who live for two periods, young and old, with an initial old that lives for one period only. Economy starts in period $t = 1$ and continues forever, denoted as $t = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \infty$. Population is divided evenly between young and old, and grows at a constant rate $n > 1$, such that population in period t is $N_t = nN_{t-1}$. Additionally, let our economy be an endowment economy, such that agents endow $y > 0$ units of consumption goods when young and nothing when old.

Let $c_{i,t}$ denote consumption at time t in period $i \in \{1,2\}$ of an agent's two periods of life. Thus, agents' lifetime utility from consumption is denoted as:

$$u(c_{1,t}, c_{2,t+1})$$

For simplification, we assume for stationary equilibrium, where all generations have identical preferences and rational expectation, hence, $c_{1,t} = c_1$ and

$c_{2,t+1} = c_2$ for all t . It is assumed that agents' utility from consumption is subject to diminishing marginal utility such that $u'' < 0 < u'$, and that c_1 and c_2 are always positive and finite, such that it satisfies the Inada conditions.

Given consumption goods are perishable thus non-storable, to finance consumption when old, young agents trade leftover endowment goods from period 1 consumption for physical money. A unit of endowment good can be traded into p_t units of physical money at time t . Therefore, we can express the unit value of physical money in terms of goods as $v_t \in \mathbb{R}_+$:

$$v_t = \frac{1}{p_t}$$

Thus, the real rate of return on physical money:

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{\frac{1}{p_{t+1}}}{\frac{1}{p_t}} = \frac{p_t}{p_{t+1}} = \frac{1}{1 + \pi} \quad (2.0)$$

Is equal to the ratio of current period's price level to next period's price level, which is equivalent to the inverse of gross inflation rate in the model economy.

2.2 Central Bank

Let M_t denote the aggregate money supply in our model economy at time t . Under our base case, this describes base money (M0) and consists of zero nominal interest yielding physical currency only. At each date $t \geq 1$, the central bank expands aggregate money supply at a constant rate of $z > 1$, which agents view as being set exogenously. Units of physical money created each period is:

$$M_t - M_{t-1} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{z}\right) M_t = (z - 1)M_{t-1}$$

Revenue from seigniorage is used to finance the fiscal authority to service lump-sum transfers to the old, given they are the user of physical money. Each old agent receive an equal amount of consumption good transfer $a_{t+1} \geq 0$.

Therefore, the central bank budget constraint in the model economy is:

$$N_{t-1}a_{t+1} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{z}\right) v_t M_t = (z - 1)v_t M_{t-1} \quad (2.1)$$

2.3 Base case optimal policies

Consider agents' problem. Taking lump-sum transfer as given, the young chooses one's acquisition of physical money in per unit goods term $v_t m_t$ such that lifetime utility is maximised, subject to their initial endowment y . Thus, let us denote individual's real demand for physical money at time t as $q_t \equiv v_t m_t$.

When old, they consume up to everything they own in $t + 1$, which includes physical money acquired when young which is now worth $v_{t+1} m_t$, and lump-sum transfer from the planner a_{t+1} . Hence, the budget constraint an agent face when young and old in our model economy is:

$$c_1 + v_t m_t \leq y \quad (2.3)$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1} m_t + a_{t+1} \quad (2.4)$$

Given utility maximising agents always consume up to the budget constraint. We rewrite 2.3 and 2.4 such that the left-hand side (LHS) and right-hand side (RHS) equate. Then, combine them to obtain the lifetime budget constraint:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) a_{t+1} \quad (2.5)$$

Now, we will compute the market clearing condition. Rearranging 2.3, an Individual agent's real demand for physical money q_t is:

$$v_t m_t = q_t = y - c_1 \quad (2.6)$$

Thus, the aggregate real demand for physical money in our base case economy at time t , is condition 2.6 multiplied by population N_t :

$$q_t N_t = N_t (y - c_1)$$

In the monetary equilibrium where physical money holds value $v_t > 0$ for all periods, market must clear such that $q_t N_t$ equates to the aggregate supply of physical money:

$$N_t (y - c_1) = v_t M_t \quad (2.7)$$

Rearranging 2.7, we derive the real rate of return of physical money¹:

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{\frac{N_{t+1}(y - c_1)}{M_{t+1}}}{\frac{N_t(y - c_1)}{M_t}} = \frac{N_{t+1}M_t}{N_tM_{t+1}} = \frac{n}{z} \quad (2.8)$$

Recall 2.0; inverse 2.8 to obtain the gross inflation rate of the economy:

$$1 + \pi = \frac{p_{t+1}}{p_t} = \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} = \frac{z}{n} \quad (2.9)$$

Given monetary (change in z) and fiscal policy (lump-sum transfer a_{t+1}) does not affect the initial endowment of the young, total resource available for consumption at period $t \in \{1, 2, \dots, \infty\}$ is $N_t y$. Thus, for the planner, who is not bounded by individual agents' budget constraints, the consumption depends only on age. Therefore, the resource constraint is given by:

$$N_t c_1 + N_{t-1} c_2 = N_t y \quad (2.10)$$

Simplify for the feasible set line:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) c_2 = y \quad (2.11)$$

With agents' utility in general forms, for the decentralised equilibrium to result in the optimal allocations described by the centralised planner solution, lifetime budget constraint 2.5 must be identical to resource constraint 2.11:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) a_{t+1} \leftrightarrow c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) c_2 = y$$

Plug in real return of money derived in 2.8:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{z}{n}\right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{z}{n}\right) a_{t+1} \leftrightarrow c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) c_2 = y$$

Thus, for the decentralised equilibrium to result in optimal allocations, the optimal monetary policy is for the central bank to not expand money supply between periods such that $z = 1$, and $a_{t+1} = 0$.

Under the optimal monetary policy, inflation rate is:

$$\pi = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{p_t} = \frac{p_{t+1}}{p_t} - 1 = \frac{1 - n}{n} < 0$$

¹ Derivation steps in Appendix A

Given growing population, the endowment economy must experience deflation under optimal monetary policy. Intuitively, given only the old hold money, and goods are endowed by the young; as there are more young agents each period, more goods will be chasing the same amount of money. Thus, one unit of physical money is worth more in the real term given supply outstrips demand:

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{p_{t+1}} > \frac{v_t}{p_t}$$

For the above condition to satisfy, price must be decreasing over time:

$$p_{t+1} < p_t$$

2.4 Central Bank with interest-bearing money

Departing from the base case, *ceteris paribus*, instead of supplying physical money only, the central bank now supplies an additional form of money to households: interest bearing digital money. CBDC yields a nominal interest rate of $i \geq 0$, which is set by the central bank and exogenously taken by households.

We take inspiration from Keister and Sanches's setup (2022) and make the simplifying assumption that apart from the additional interest earning on digital currency, both physical and CBDC holds the same convenience value. This implies that they are equally widely accepted and the cost of holding (e.g., app versus physical storage) are the same. This ensures that for agents, holding CBDC is equivalent to holding a physical money that earns a gross interest of $(1 + i)$ instead of 1. With this, we can modify the real rate of return of physical money in condition 2.0:

$$(1 + i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \tag{2.12}$$

This gives the real rate of return on CBDC. We discuss the implication of this in Lemma 2 and 3.

In what follows, let M_t consists of CBDC only. The fiscal government continues to provide lump-sum transfer to old agents like the base case, whilst the monetary government must expense the interest rate payout of CBDC. Thus, in addition to seigniorage, government expenditure is backed by

taxation, in a lump-sum form such that it is not distortionary. Therefore, the government budget constraint becomes:

$$v_t(M_t - M_{t-1}) = v_t(iM_{t-1}) + N_{t-1}T_t \quad (2.13)$$

Where LHS of 2.13 denotes revenue of the government, obtained through seigniorage. The RHS denotes the expenditure, which is made up of interest expense in real term $v_t(iM_{t-1})$ and aggregate net lumpsum transfer/tax $N_{t-1}T_t$.

Constraint 2.13 simplifies to:

$$v_t M_{t-1}(z - 1 - i) = N_{t-1}T_t$$

Unlike a_{t+1} in government constraint 2.1, T_t can either be positive or negative. $T_t > 0$ if seigniorage alone is enough to cover interest payments, and households receive a lump-sum transfer in this scenario. Otherwise, households will receive a lump-sum tax; in which case, $T_t < 0$. By equating LHS and RHS, we state that government must clear its monetary and fiscal expenditures with revenue from seigniorage and taxation. With this setup, we ensure that there is no inflationary effect from central banks paying out interest on CBDC.

Lemma 1: *Without government budget constraint 2.13, expensing CBDC becomes inflationary, and CBDC yields the same return as physical money.*

Proof: Suppose interest expenditure is not fiscally backed by taxation, the only way for the monetary authority to fund for it is to raise more seigniorage revenue, by increasing the rate at which money supply grows ($z \uparrow$), which is inflationary.

This changes the return of digital money. For the government to clear their balance, the rate of growth in money supply between two periods is required to be:

$$\frac{M_{t+1}}{M_t} = z(1 + i)$$

Given constant population growth n and money supply growth $z(1 + i)$, the real rate of return on CBDC in condition 2.12 becomes:

$$(1 + i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = (1 + i) \cdot \frac{N_{t+1}M_t}{N_t M_{t+1}} = \frac{(1 + i)n}{(1 + i)z} = \frac{n}{z} \quad (2.14)$$

Comparing 2.14 to 2.8, we see physical and digital money yield the same return. This implies that the increase in next period value for CBDC from bearing interest is cancelled out by the expansionary effect it has on money supply, given the interest is funded by money creation.

Lemma 2: *If constraint 2.13 holds, and $T_t > 0$, return of CBDC strictly dominates physical money.*

Proof: If $T_t > 0$, when we compare real rate of return of two types of money, we can say with certainty that the return of digital money (LHS of condition 2.15) is greater than the return of physical money (RHS of condition 2.15):

$$(1 + i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} > \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \quad (2.15)$$

This is because i is set to be strictly positive in our model. We should expect utility maximising and risk neutral agents to choose the medium of exchange with the highest return. Thus, when $T_t > 0$, condition 2.15 suggests physical money is replaced by CBDC.

Lemma 3: *If constraint 2.13 holds, and $T_t < 0$, we can no longer say with certainty that the return of CBDC strictly dominates physical money, and it is possible for the return of CBDC to be dominated by physical money, as interest i increases.*

Proof: Rearrange condition 2.13 to derive function for net lump-sum transfer/tax:

$$\frac{v_t M_{t-1} (z - 1 - i)}{N_{t-1}} = T_t \quad (2.16)$$

Take first-order condition of 2.16 to interest rate:

$$\frac{dT_t}{di} = -\frac{v_t M_{t-1}}{N_{t-1}} < 0$$

Net lump-sum transfer/tax is decreasing to an increasing in interest on CBDC. The net payoff for an agent to exchange m_t quantity of digital money when $T_{t+1} < 0$ is:

$$(1 + i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} m_t + T_{t+1} \leq \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} m_t + a_{t+1} \quad (2.17)$$

When i increases, T_{t+1} decrease at a faster rate than increase in $(1+i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} m_t$ ². Thus, the higher i becomes, the smaller LHS of condition 2.17 will be, which means condition 2.17 becomes more likely to hold, suggesting that physical money either weakly or strictly dominates CBDC.

Intuitively, when $T_{t+1} < 0$, revenue from seigniorage can no longer cover for interest expense on CBDC, such that households now bear the burden for the interest expense, and no longer receive a transfer when old. Eventually, there will be a point that agents are made worse-off for holding CBDC, despite its higher return. We elaborate on this in chapter 3.4.

2.5 CBDC case optimal policies

Following our assumption that M_t consists of CBDC only, redefine $v_t m_t$ as one's acquisition of CBDC in real term. The young chooses one's holding of CBDC m_t to maximise lifetime utility $u(c_1, c_2)$, subject to:

$$c_1 + v_t m_t \leq y \quad (2.18)$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}(1+i)m_t + T_{t+1} \quad (2.19)$$

The second period budget constraint now includes both the interest earning and lump-sum transfer/tax. Substituting 2.18 into 2.19 gives CBDC economy's lifetime budget constraint³:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i} \right) T_{t+1} \quad (2.20)$$

Given 2.18 is identical to 2.3, the condition for the monetary equilibrium in CBDC case does not change from the one we derived in the base case:

$$N_t(y - c_1) = v_t M_t$$

Recall 2.12, derive the real rate of return for CBDC:

$$(1+i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = (1+i) \cdot \frac{\frac{N_{t+1}(y - c_1)}{M_{t+1}}}{\frac{N_t(y - c_1)}{M_t}} = \frac{(1+i)N_{t+1}M_t}{N_t M_{t+1}} = \frac{(1+i)n}{z} \quad (2.21)$$

² We show this graphically in figure 1

³ Derivation steps in Appendix B

Like the base case, implementing interest and lump-sum tax does not impact aggregate endowment. Thus, the resource constraint is identical to the base case given by 2.11:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)c_2 \leq y$$

To achieve golden rule allocation described by the resource constraint, lifetime budget constraint 2.20 must be identical to the resource constraint above.

Substituting in $(1+i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{(1+i)n}{z}$ derived in 2.21:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{z}{(1+i)n}\right)c_2 \leq y + \left(\frac{z}{(1+i)n}\right)T_{t+1} \leftrightarrow c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)c_2 \leq y$$

Therefore, the net lump-sum transfer/tax T_{t+1} must equal to zero, such that seigniorage revenue $M_t(z-1)$ is only used to finance interest rate expenditure. To achieve this, constant rate of money stock expansion must equate to the gross nominal rate of interest on CBDC. Hence, the optimal fiscal and monetary policies are:

$$T_{t+1} = 0$$

$$z = 1 + i$$

And optimal inflation is given by:

$$\pi = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{p_t} = \frac{p_{t+1}}{p_t} - 1 = \frac{1-n}{n} < 0$$

We observe that in both the base case and CBDC case, the economy must experience deflation, independent of whether the central bank supplies physical money only or a combination of CBDC with physical money.

3 Equilibrium

In this chapter, we discuss the implication of introducing interest-bearing CBDC on allocations, by comparing it to the base case with physical money only. To enable our analysis, let households' preference be:

$$u(c_1, c_2) = (c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The utility function suggests consumption when young and old are viewed as perfect substitutes to one another. Preference exhibits characteristic of

positive but diminishing marginal return and the substitution effect from interest rate changes dominate the income effect. Thus, if the rate of return for money goes up due to higher interest, more CBDC should be demanded as a result.

3.1 Calibration

Table 1 summarises the calibration of parameters. In our benchmark model, we introduced a total of 4 parameters: π^e, n, z, y . For the ease of analysis, all calibrations are set under the assumption that the government targets a stable inflation rate of 2%. Thus, in the short-run where prices are rigid given nominal stickiness, inflation expectations is modelled as a constant:

$$\pi^e = \pi_T = 2\%$$

Given budget constraint 2.13 holds, following lemma 1, the rate of inflation will be identical between both economies. This simplifies our analysis on interest rate, given lowering the nominal interest rate will result in the real interest rate being lowered too.

For constant population growth parameter n , we used ONS's official population projections (2024), and estimated that the UK population will grow year-on-year at a constant rate of 0.57%. Thus, we can calculate the optimal monetary policy stance z required to achieve 2% inflation, using condition 2.9:

$$1 + \pi^e = 1.02 = \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} = \frac{z}{n}$$

Simplify:

$$\pi^e = 2\% = \frac{z}{n} - 1$$

$$z = n(\pi^e + 1)$$

Substituting in $n = 0.57\%$:

$$z = 1.02612$$

Lastly, following the Median gross annual earnings for full-time employees in the UK, provided by the ONS (2023), the identical initial endowment of individuals y is set to be 35, unit in thousands of sterling.

Table 1: Parameter calibration

Households		
$u(c_1)$	Agents' first period utility function	$(c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}}$
$u(c_2)$	Agents' second period utility function	$(c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$
y	Initial endowment (pounds, thousands)	35
Environment		
n	Population growth rate	1.006
Government		
π^e	Expected nominal inflation	2%
z	Growth rate of money supply	1.026

3.2 Base case

The initial old and all future generations have identical preferences described in the functional form below:

$$u(c_1, c_2) = (c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Subject to the transformed budget constraint containing real physical money demand q_t :

$$c_1 + q_t \leq y \tag{3.0}$$

$$c_2 \leq \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \tag{3.1}$$

Thus, the unconstrained maximisation problem is given by:

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The first-order condition of agents' problem with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2} (y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0 \tag{3.2}$$

Rearrange 3.2, solve for real demand of physical money q_t , consumption when young c_1 and old c_2 . Substituting in real rate of return of physical money $\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}$ derived in 2.8 yields⁴:

$$q = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}} \left(\frac{n}{z} y - \frac{z a_{t+1}}{n} \right)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}} \left(y + \frac{z a_{t+1}}{n} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{z}{n} + 1} \left(\frac{n}{z} y + a_{t+1} \right)$$

With equilibrium solutions above, we can derive the per-person lump-sum transfer, which is funded by seigniorage. Recall government budget constraint 2.1 and rearrange so it becomes a function of a_{t+1} :

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{\frac{n(z-1)}{z} v_{t+1} M_{t+1}}{N_{t+1}}$$

Substitute in the money market clearing condition, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1} M_{t+1}$:

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{n(z-1)(y - c_1)}{z}$$

Now, substitute in q to solve for a ⁵:

$$a = \frac{n^2(z-1)}{z(z^2 + n)} y$$

Thus, we have obtained the equilibrium level of lump-sum transfer for our base case economy.

Lemma 4: *A positive increase in population growth rate n results in a decrease in consumption when young.*

Proof: Take the equilibrium level c_1 , and derive the first-order condition to population growth rate:

$$\frac{dc_1}{dn} = - \frac{z(yn^2 + 2zna_{t+1} + z^2 a_{t+1})}{n^2(n+z)^2} < 0$$

⁴ Derivation steps in Appendix D

⁵ Derivation steps in Appendix C

Thus, consumption when young is decreasing to an increase in rate of population growth. Intuition is the same as the conclusion of chapter 2.3. Given value of money is increasing over time, return from exchanging goods is increasing. Thus, utility maximising agents decrease c_1 .

We arrive at the same conclusion when observing the optimality condition. Rearrange condition 3.2 and plug in return of physical money derived in 2.8:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{n}{z}q_t + a_{t+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{u'(c_1)}{u'(c_2)} = \frac{n}{z} \quad (3.3)$$

Condition 3.3 captures that, utility maximising demand for physical money occurs when the marginal rate of substitution between consumption when young and old is equal to the rate of return of physical money. In general form, the optimality equation is given by:

$$zu'(c_1) = nu'(c_2) \quad (3.4)$$

Thus, marginal utility from consuming when old (LHS of condition 3.3) is increasing to n .

3.3 CBDC case

The agents' problem in the CBDC economy is subject to:

$$c_1 + q_t \leq y \quad (3.5)$$

$$c_2 \leq \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \quad (3.6)$$

Substituting the above into agents' utility function gives the unconstrained problem:

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+i)q_t + T_{t+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

First-order conditions with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2}(y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2}\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+i)\left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+i)q_t + T_{t+1}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0 \quad (3.7)$$

Now, solve for q_t , c_1 and c_2 . Substituting in real rate of return of physical money $\frac{(1+i)v_{t+1}}{v_t}$ in 2.21 yields⁶:

$$q = \frac{1}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \left(y \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] - \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1+i)} \right)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \left[y + \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1+i)} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{z}{n(1+i)}} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i)y + T_{t+1} \right]$$

Like the base case, solve for equilibrium level of net lump-sum transfer/tax, T . Recall government budget constraint 2.13 and rearrange so T_{t+1} is the subject:

$$\frac{v_{t+1}M_t(z-1-i)}{N_t} = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute in the money market clearing condition, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1}M_{t+1}$:

$$(y - c_1)(z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

Now, substitute the equilibrium level of real CBDC demand q to solve for T ⁷:

$$\frac{(z - 1 - i) \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right]^2 y}{\left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right) (1+i) + (z - 1 - i)} = T$$

Thus, we have obtained the equilibrium level of lump-sum transfer/tax of our CBDC case economy.

Lemma 5: *Marginal utility from consuming when old is increasing to an increase in interest rate for CBDC.*

Proof: Rearrange condition 3.7 and plug in real return of CBDC derived in 2.21 gives us the condition for utility maximising demand of CBDC:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{u'(c_1)}{u'(c_2)} = \frac{n(1+i)}{z} \quad (3.8)$$

⁶ Derivation steps in Appendix E

⁷ Derivation steps in Appendix C (part 2)

Optimality condition 3.8 mostly mirrors 3.3, with the addition of gross interest rate on CBDC, which increases the present value of second period consumption:

$$zu'(c_1) = n(1 + i)u'(c_2) \uparrow$$

3.4 Short-run market allocations

For our endowment economy, we define output to be equivalent to the young exchanging their initial endowment good (market good) for money; and that leisure is equivalent to agents consuming their initial endowment (non-market good), such that they are not engaging in the exchange of goods.

Let us observe the impact on utility in the short-run, where inflation is fixed:

Figure 1: Base vs. CBDC - utility

Shown by the LHS chart of figure 1, the utility maximising level of nominal interest rate when z is fixed given 2% inflation expectation, is at 2.6%. This aligns with our optimal policy analysis: i^* should equate to the rate of money supply growth. And, as shown by the RHS chart, net lump-sum transfer/tax is equal to 0:

$$T_t = 0$$

$$i^* = z - 1 = 1.026 - 1 = 0.026$$

Additionally, utility is concave to the interest rate on digital currency. This is due to the cost of financing interest-bearing CBDC in the form of taxation,

which is borne by the household. We see that if the policy rate for CBDC goes beyond 2.6%, utility starts to trend downwards, as T becomes a tax burden (negative) as shown in the RHS of figure 1. Intuitively, this is because to ensure there is no inflationary pressure from expensing interest rate, the government must fund its expenditure by taxing households ($T < 0$). The moment we go beyond i^* , for every unit of increase in interest rate, T will reduce at a greater rate than the benefit gained from interest, in the form of higher rate of return on money, which translates into higher second period consumption. When $5.3\% > i > i^*$, despite not being pareto efficient, CBDC still strictly dominates base case with physical cash only.

Agents become indifferent between a CBDC economy and a physical money only economy when the nominal interest rate for CBDC is either equal to 0% or reaches 5.3%. When $i = 0$, CBDC earns no interest and becomes identical to physical money, thus agents experience same level of welfare in both cases. When $i = 5.3\%$, to satisfy government budget constraint, households loses the same amount of consumption from the lump-sum tax as they would have gained from the higher return on money. Our conclusion is in line with Davoodalhosseini (2020), who had a similar setup where both cash and CBDC can be held; if the cost of CBDC is small, only CBDC is used under optimal policy. Thus, at critical threshold where CBDC becomes too costly characterised by $i \geq 5.3\%$, physical money weakly dominates CBDC, as suggested in lemma 3.

Figure 2: Base vs. CBDC – output and leisure

Next, let us observe the impact of CBDC on output and leisure. In figure 2, CBDC and physical money economy intercepts when $i = 0$. This is because given our earlier assumption that apart from the interest rate, both monies are identical in all other aspect. Thus, if CBDC yields zero nominal interest, the allocation of output and leisure becomes identical.

Given the return of money is higher in the CBDC economy as long as $i > 0$, utility maximising agents would choose to demand more money, through exchanging marketable endowment goods for CBDC. Therefore, as shown by the LHS chart of figure 2, output is strictly increasing to interest rate, which means leisure must be traded-off. Thus, in the RHS chart, leisure is strictly decreasing to interest rate.

4 Banking model

Given the status quo is for monetary policy to be implemented through the banking sector, we modify the benchmark model to have deposit as the only medium of exchange. We denote this as the deposit case.

4.1 Households

For our banking economy, let its environment remain identical to the base economy. Their utility in stationary equilibrium is given by:

$$u(c_1, c_2)$$

By introducing a banking sector, households now have access to a new type of money: commercial bank money, in the form of deposits, which will always yield a positive interest of $r \geq 0$. With characteristics of the endowment good remaining the same, to finance consumption when old, the young need to exchange one unit of endowment into p_t units of deposits at a commercial bank, which then earns a gross interest of $1 + r$.

In what follows, let us assume that households use deposits as the only means of payment. Like CBDC, for ease of comparison, we make the simplifying assumption that apart from the additional interest earning, both deposits and physical currency hold the same convenience value, cost of holding and is equally widely accepted. We discuss the implication and justification for this

assumption in more detail at the end of chapter 4.2. This assumption ensure that the act of holding deposit is equivalent to holding a physical money that earns a gross interest of $(1 + r)$ instead of 1. Thus, let us modify the real rate of return of physical currency in 2.0 to display the real rate of return of deposits:

$$(1 + r) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \tag{4.0}$$

4.2 Banking sector

Let M_t be the aggregate money supply in our model at time t , which describes broad money M4. Given our assumption earlier stating households hold deposits only, the central bank's liability is made up of reserves only. Reserve is interest deriving deposits from the commercial banks saved with the central bank. Let us denote the nominal interest paid to the commercial banks for reserve as i , which is strictly positive and set by the central bank as a policy tool. This is equivalent to bank rate in a real-world context, exogenously taken by the commercial banks. For ease of comparison, let the interest paid to the commercial banks for reserve be the same as the interest on a digital currency. In alignment with the real-world, households have no way of accessing central bank money in deposit case.

At each date $t \geq 1$, the central bank expands aggregate money supply, in the form of reserves, at a constant rate of $z > 1$. The revenue from seigniorage is used to fund fiscal policy of lump-sum transfer to the old, and expense the interest paid to commercial banks for their reserves. When the revenue from seigniorage is unable to fully cover the interest expense on reserve, the central bank will implement a lump-sum tax on the households to clear their balance. Therefore, we can express the central bank budget constraint as:

$$v_t M_{t-1} (z - 1 - i) = N_{t-1} T_t \tag{4.1}$$

Where T_t denotes the net lump-sum transfer/tax in real term, such that if $T_t > 0$, it suggests that revenue from seigniorage clears interest expense on reserve, and that each old agent at time t receives an equal amount of consumption good transfer T_t . If $T_t < 0$, it suggests that revenue from seigniorage is not enough to clear interest expense of reserves, and thus a lump-sum tax of T_t in terms of consumption good is placed on the old.

The banking sector in our economy funds interest on deposits using interest paid on reserves. For simplicity, let our banking sector consist of 1 representative commercial bank only. Suppose homogenous agents' real demand for money per person at time t is $q_t \equiv v_t d_t$, thus on aggregate, the economy deposits $d_t N_t$ quantity of money at the representative commercial bank in period t . The representative commercial bank then invests all deposits they hold in the current period into reserves such that in the next period, they earn in real term:

$$v_{t+1} d_t N_t (1 + i)$$

This denotes the revenue of our representative bank in period $t + 1$. Then, the commercial bank clears its "I owe you" obligations with agents by paying back their deposit d_t with a gross interest of $(1 + r)$ for each unit of deposit held, such that their cost in $t + 1$ is:

$$v_{t+1} d_t N_t (1 + r)$$

Thus, profit function of the representative commercial bank is:

$$\Pi_{t+1} = v_{t+1} d_t N_t (i - r) \tag{4.2}$$

Let μ be the transmission parameter between bank rate on reserves i , and the deposit rate r , characterised by the range $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$. Thus, the relationship between bank rate and deposit rate is given by:

$$\mu i = r \tag{4.3}$$

In the real-world context, μ describes the extend of which monetary policy rate changes from the central bank is passed through to deposit rates. μ is influenced by various characteristics of the banking sector, like the sector's concentration which determines market power, liquidity, and availability of deposits relative to profitable lending opportunities (IMF, 2024). Given the lack of alternative opportunities, let μ be predominantly influenced by market power of the banking sector, as others are out of the scope of our model.

For simplicity, let μ be exogenously taken by all participants (households, commercial and central bank). We will discuss implications of different level of μ in chapter 5.

Substituting condition 4.3 into 4.2, we construct the unconstrained profit maximising problem subject to deposit rate:

$$\max_r v_{t+1} d_t N_t \left(\frac{r}{\mu} - r \right)$$

When $\mu = 1$, the representative bank makes normal profit; and the closer μ is to zero, the bigger the super normal profit the representative bank makes become.

Let us set a regulatory constraint which ensures that all profits made by the commercial bank will not be transmitted to agents, instead it will be held in terms of liquidity in case of early or speculative withdraws⁸. This assumption ensures the commercial bank is prudent, given our simplified model has no alternative asset and liabilities apart from reserve and deposits. Having a liquidity coverage ratio (LCR) under Basel III simplifies the model and ensures agents that all short-term obligations will be met, which allows for the assumption that there will be no runs in our deposit as medium of exchange economy. Therefore, linking back to our earlier assumption, this regulatory requirement will eliminate the risk associated with bank deposits, such that it makes sense for agents to be indifferent between all monies.

Another implication of our setup is that a banking sector with market power strictly makes households worse-off. If the commercial bank are owned by the households such that all bank profits can be consumed, agents can still benefit from the profit even when policy pass-through is not perfect ($\mu < 1$). However, the regulatory constraint means that not only households will suffer from the lower rate of return on money given interest on reserve is discounted, but they will also not be able to consume profits from a non-perfectly competitive banking sector.

Lemma 6: *Suppose banks are owned by households and there is no regulatory requirement for banks to re-invest profits into a liquidity buffer. If households evenly distributed profit made by the commercial bank, then no matter what the transmission parameter is, households will always be equally as well-off as the CBDC economy.*

⁸ Alternatively to LCR, a deposit insurance scheme where profits are collected by the government to fund for the insurance, will also achieve the same outcome.

Proof: The share of profits received by an old agent is:

$$\frac{\Pi_{t+1}}{N_t} = \frac{v_{t+1}d_t N_t(i-r)}{N_t} = v_{t+1}d_t(i-r)$$

Rewrite second period budget constraint to include profit of the commercial bank:

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}(1+r)d_t + T_{t+1} + v_{t+1}d_t(i-r)$$

Simplify:

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}d_t(1+i) + T_{t+1}$$

The first period budget constraint remains unchanged. Rearrange budget constraint when old to have d_t as the subject, and substitute into budget constraint when young to obtain the lifetime budget constraint⁹:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i}\right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i}\right) T_{t+1}$$

Now, compare the deposit economy's lifetime budget constraint when the old can consume profit of the commercial bank, against the CBDC economy's lifetime budget constraint 2.2.0:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i}\right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i}\right) T_{t+1}$$

Given the interest on reserve is the same as interest set on CBDC, lifetime budget constraints are identical. Thus, *ceteris paribus*, if households has identical preference, agents in both economies will have the same unconstrained maximisation problem, thus the same equilibrium allocation.

Intuitively, this means that profit made from imperfect policy passthrough exactly makes up for the losses from lower interest rate, regardless of the level of μ . However, it is unrealistic to assume profit made by the commercial bank is evenly distributed to all agents. Hence, given the focus of our analysis is on households' portfolio choices when CBDC is introduced, we stick to the original setup which does not allow pass through of profits made by the banking sector.

⁹ Derivation steps in Appendix F

4.3 Optimal policies with banking

Let $v_t d_t$ be one's acquisition of deposits in real term. The young chooses one's holding of deposits at commercial bank d_t to maximise lifetime utility $u(c_1, c_2)$, subject to:

$$c_1 + v_t d_t \leq y \quad (4.4)$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}(1+r)d_t + T_{t+1} \quad (4.5)$$

With utility maximising agents consuming up to the budget constraint, use condition 4.3, rewrite deposit rate in terms of bank rate, and construct the lifetime budget constraint of agents¹⁰:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+\mu i} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+\mu i} \right) T_{t+1} \quad (4.6)$$

Given budget constraint when young remains unchanged, we can take market clearing condition 2.7:

$$N_t(y - c_1) = v_t M_t$$

And derive the real rate of return of deposits using 4.0:

$$(1+r) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = (1+r) \cdot \frac{\frac{N_{t+1}(y-c_1)}{M_{t+1}}}{\frac{N_t(y-c_1)}{M_t}} = \frac{(1+r)N_{t+1}M_t}{N_t M_{t+1}} = \frac{(1+r)n}{z}$$

The return of deposits in terms of policy rate is given by:

$$(1+\mu i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z} \quad (4.7)$$

As seen in the CBDC case, implementing deposit interest and lump-sum tax does not impact initial endowment. Thus, the resource constraint is identical to 2.11:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) c_2 = y$$

To achieve golden rule allocation, lifetime budget constraint 4.6 must be identical to resource constraint above.

¹⁰ Derivation steps in Appendix F (part 2)

Substituting in $(1 + \mu i) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z}$:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{z}{(1 + \mu i)n} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{z}{(1 + \mu i)n} \right) T_{t+1} \leftrightarrow c_1 + \left(\frac{1}{n} \right) c_2 \leq y$$

Similar to the CBDC case, lump-sum transfer/tax must equal to zero, such that seigniorage revenue $M_t(z - 1)$ is used to fund the gross interest rate on reserve only. Therefore, optimal monetary and fiscal policy is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{t+1} &= 0 \\ z &= 1 + \mu i \end{aligned} \tag{4.8}$$

When $\mu = 1$, optimality conditions are identical between CBDC and deposit case. Condition 4.8 suggests that the more market power the commercial bank has ($\mu \downarrow$), the slower the rate of money supply expansion should be.

Optimal inflation is given by:

$$\pi = \frac{p_{t+1} - p_t}{p_t} = \frac{p_{t+1}}{p_t} - 1 = \frac{1 - n}{n} < 0$$

5 Equilibrium with banking sector

In this chapter, we solve for the market equilibrium when deposit is the only medium of exchange economy. Then, taking μ as given, we discuss implications of having different levels of interest. Lastly, we analyse the implication of having different levels of transmission parameter μ , and whether households can be equally as well-off when compared to the CBDC and base case.

5.1 Deposit case

The initial old and all future generations have the same utility function used in chapter 3:

$$u(c_1, c_2) = (c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Subject to:

$$c_1 + q_t \leq y \tag{5.0}$$

$$c_2 \leq \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1 + r)q_t + T_{t+1} \tag{5.1}$$

Substitute 5.0 and 5.1 into the utility function to construct the unconstrained maximisation problem:

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1 + r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

First-order conditions with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2}(y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1 + r) \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1 + r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0 \quad (5.2)$$

Now, solve for q_t , c_1 and c_2 . Substituting in real rate of return of deposits $\frac{(1+r)v_{t+1}}{v_t}$ derived in 4.6 yields¹¹:

$$q = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i)} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i)y - \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)} \right]$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i)} \left[y + \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{z}{n(1 + \mu i)} + 1} \left[\frac{n(1 + \mu i)}{z}y + T_{t+1} \right]$$

Lastly, solve for the equilibrium level of net lump-sum transfer/tax T .

Rearrange government budget constraint 4.1 so it becomes a function of T_{t+1} :

$$\frac{v_{t+1}M_t(z - 1 - i)}{N_t} = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute in the market clearing condition, which is identical between economies, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1}M_{t+1}$:

$$(y - c_1)(z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute in the equilibrium level of real deposit demand q to solve for T ¹²:

$$\frac{(z - 1 - i) \left[\frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i) \right]^2 y}{\left[1 + \frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i) \right] (1 + \mu i) + (z - 1 - i)} = T$$

Thus, we have obtained the equilibrium level of lump-sum transfer/tax in our deposit case.

¹¹ Derivation steps in Appendix G

¹² Derivation steps in Appendix H

5.2 Perfect pass-through

When transmission parameter $\mu = 1$, interest set for reserve is transmitted perfectly to agents' consumption and output choices. Thus, allocation of endowment goods align to what we would expect a-priori, households are indifference between having access to interest-bearing central bank money, or deposits from the commercial bank.

Given banks cannot make loses such that μ is capped at 1, we can define the equilibrium when CBDC bears $i = 2.6\%$ as pareto optimal, as there is no way to improve households' welfare further under our model setup ($\pi^e = 2\%$).

Figure 3: Base vs. CBDC vs. Deposit— perfect transmission

As shown by figure 3, curves for CBDC and deposit case perfectly aligns, and all observations made in chapter 3.4 holds true here.

For households, reducing interest below $i^* = 2.6\%$ lowers the return of deposit, which means there is less of an incentive for households to exchange endowment goods into deposits (output reduces) and vice versa. For the banking sector, as stated in chapter 4, perfect transmission suggests the commercial bank operates with no profit, such that household's utility is maximised, earning the reserve interest rate. Households' welfare in deposit case starts to decline once $T < 0$. When $i < 5.3\%$, households strictly prefer CBDC and deposits to physical money; when $i \geq 5.3\%$, physical money weakly dominates other monies.

5.3 Imperfect pass-through

When transmission between bank rate and deposit rate is imperfect ($\mu < 1$), we see households are strictly worse-off, even at the utility maximising level, compared to the CBDC case.

Figure 4: CBDC vs. deposit - utility

Utility maximising interest on reserve described by condition 4.8, is given by:

$$\frac{z - 1}{\mu} = i \quad (5.3)$$

In figure 4 where $\mu = 0.99$, following condition 5.3, utility maximising interest should be at 2.62%. This is higher than the optimal interest (2.6%) on reserve at perfect transmission, to compensate for the incomplete bank (policy) rate pass-through to households. This contradicts our graphical analysis, which states the utility-maximising rate is 1.6%. This mismatch is because of the government budget constraint.

Let us suppose reserve rate is set at 2.62%. Given $\mu = 0.99$, households receive a discounted interest of 2.6%. Now, if this is the CBDC economy, when household receives an interest of 2.6%, as shown by figure 1, $T = 0$. However, because households hold deposits, not CBDC, they are taxed, as shown by figure 5:

Figure 5: lump-sum tax/transfer at different transmission rate

This is because central bank funds for the reserve interest rate, not the deposit rate. Therefore, if bank rate is set at 2.62%, we do not satisfy the optimality condition for fiscal policy, which requires $T = 0$. Additionally, given lump-sum tax only marginally increases with μ , as long as $i \neq 2.6\%$, we will not be able satisfy fiscal optimality of $T = 0$. Thus, to satisfy both monetary and fiscal optimality, μ must equal to 1, which marks perfect transmission and no market power to the banking sector. This implies when banking sector has market power, it is impossible for households to reach pareto optimal equilibrium.

For households to maximise utility when $\mu < 1$, interest on reserve must be set at a lower level than 2.6%, to ensure $T > 0$, given T declines quicker than increase in return on deposits from i increasing.

This mismatch between reserve which needs to be funded and return on deposit is also why we see an earlier and steeper decline in which households in deposit economy becomes worse-off than base economy in figure 4.

Let us now compare T in CBDC and deposit economy. Intuitively, when interest is low, one would think that T received by agents in the deposit economy is higher given the reduced demand for deposit, which should decrease the cost of interest expense, allowing for more money towards lump-sum transfer. However, this is not always the case:

Figure 6: Difference in lump-sum transfer/tax

As shown in figure 6, our intuition is true only when nominal interest is above optimal level. When interest is below i^* , lump-sum subsidy received by agents is lower in the deposit case compared to the CBDC case. There are two effects at work here.

First, this is because the amount of seigniorage revenue the government makes is lower, even when both economies have the same monetary policy stance.

When $\mu < 1$, at the same level of bank rate, return of deposit $\frac{(1+r)v_{t+1}}{v_t}$ is lower than return of CBDC $\frac{(1+i)v_{t+1}}{v_t}$. Thus, rational agents will demand less deposits than they would demand CBDC ($q \downarrow$). Given aggregate supply M_t must clear aggregate demand $N_t q_t$ in the monetary equilibrium such that interest on reserve equates to policy rate: if q lowers, M_t must also be lower. This is captured by the market clearing equation:

$$N_t q_t \downarrow = v_t M_t \downarrow$$

Hence, seigniorage revenue:

$$(z - 1)M_{t-1} \downarrow$$

Must decrease given lower M_t and a constant z . Recall the government budget constraint for the deposit economy:

$$v_t(z - 1 - i)M_{t-1} \downarrow = N_{t-1}T_t \downarrow$$

If the revenue from seigniorage is lower (LHS), *ceteris paribus*, the amount of budget which government can allocate to lump-sum transfer after paying-off interest on reserve must also be lower compared to the CBDC case. Thus, T is decreasing to a decrease in i .

The second effect at work here is what we had stated previously. The funding needed for the central bank to expense interest on reserve should be lowered, given money demand in deposit economy is strictly lower than CBDC economy when $\mu < 1$. Thus, T is increasing to a decrease in i .

When $i < i^*$, the positive effect which reduce interest expenditure and allow for more expansionary fiscal policies, is dominated by the negative impact from lower seigniorage revenue. However, as shown by the concavity of the lump-sum transfer/tax curve, if policy rate for both economies increases to $i > i^*$, the positive effect of tax saving given lower demand for money will dominate the negative effect from lower seigniorage. Thus, we can conclude that when interest is higher than the optimal nominal rate of 2.6%, T in the deposit economy will be lower than the CBDC economy. Additionally, by comparing the slope of the two curves in figure 6, we observe that the weaker the policy pass-through, the bigger the gap in T between economies. This is because both positive and negative effect becomes more accentuate.

Outcome on allocation of endowment goods for the deposit case is as expected when $\mu < 1$:

Figure 7: Base vs. CBDC vs. Deposit – output and leisure

Illustrated by figure 7, given the return on money is lower, households will exchange less goods for money and consume more endowment good when young compared to the CBDC case.

Let us now observe the impact of different transmission rate, on households' utility given the central bank adopts optimal policy rate, such that interest on reserve and interest on CBDC is 2.6% when $\pi^e = 2\%$.

Figure 8: Utility given transmission rate

As shown in figure 8, if $\mu < 1$, deposit will be strictly dominated by CBDC. When transmission rate is lower than 0.987, households are made worse-off by not being able to access physical money, despite the interest earning on deposits. This is because $T = 0$ in deposit case, whilst $a = 0.436$ in base case, and the higher return of deposits does not compensate for this gap. When $\mu = 0.987$, discounted earning from holding deposit in terms of consumption goods equates the amount received in the form of lump-sum transfer in the base economy.

This finding has important policy implication. Our model suggests that if transmission is imperfect, utility maximising agents will switch to CBDC if it is made available as a means of payment in the deposit economy. Money in circulation would increase as a result and we should expect deposits to be crowded out completely. More interestingly, given our government budget constraint setup, if $\mu < 0.987$, households would rather hold physical money over deposits.

Figure 9: Output and leisure given transmission rate

When $\mu < 1$, at optimal bank rate i^* , the model predicts lower output, and higher leisure in the deposit case compared to when households have access to CBDC. Compared to the base case, the model predicts higher output, and lower leisure when deposit is the only means of payment, even when $\mu = 0$, which implies households receive no interest for their deposits and that the commercial bank pockets all interest earning from reserve. This is because when $\pi^e = 2\%$, for our base economy, the old receives a positive lump-sum transfer. However, in the deposit case, $T < 0$ when $i = 2.6\%$. Thus, given positive diminishing marginal return, as the old receives no lump-sum transfer, marginal utility from consumption in second period must be higher than consuming an additional unit of endowment good when young. Thus, it is utility maximising for the young in the deposit case to exchange endowment goods for money up to a point so that they can consume when old. This is why when $\mu = 0$, despite deposits having the same return as physical money, output in the deposit case is higher than the base case in figure 10.

5.4 Implication on monetary policy efficiency

When looking at the UK post-pandemic hiking cycle, we see the ratio of pass-through between changes in policy rate and overnight deposits is 0.37% (IMF, 2024), at which our stylised model predicts that households welfare can be improved by introducing CBDC and physical money. Let $\mu = 0.37$. Suppose the central bank wants to increase output in our endowment economy, thus

implements a 50 basis-point rate hike, *ceteris paribus*. Assuming $i = 2.5\%$ in current period. Given this policy, households who hold CBDC only will increase demand for money by 0.49%, decrease leisure by 0.34% and utility will increase by $4.3 \times 10^{-4}\%$. Households with deposit as medium of exchange will increase demand for money by 0.34%, decrease leisure by 0.48% and utility will decrease by 0.07%.

Our result implies that by having imperfect transmission, disruption in agents' welfare is greater in a deposit only economy, whilst the magnitude of change in output is smaller compared to CBDC economy, given return on deposits is discounted. Thus, policy is less effective at inducing changes in allocation in an imperfect transmission deposit economy. Our model, however, is highly stylised which ignores possible real-world policy constraints¹³.

5.5 Adjusting to inflation

In previous chapters, we observed short-run implications of introducing CBDC on households' welfare, when inflation expectation is constant. We now analyse how three economies compare when π^e is no longer fixed at 2%, such that monetary policy stance z is a variable given by $z = n(\pi^e + 1)$.

Figure 10: utility at different inflation

¹³ A possible policy constraint is a cap which limits the amount of CBDC accessible per user (Bank of England, 2024), which affects households' portfolio choice and reduces effectiveness of the policy.

Starting with the CBDC economy, as seen in figure 10, if interest on CBDC is set according to the monetary optimality condition: $i^* = z - 1$, utility of households remains constant to an increase in π^e . Recall real rate of return for CBDC derived in 2.21 and substitute for i^* :

$$(1 + i^*) \cdot \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{(1 + i^*)}{1 + \pi^e} = \frac{(1 + i^*)n}{z} = \frac{[1 + (z - 1)]n}{z} = n \quad (5.4)$$

We see that the real return of CBDC is unaffected by money supply growth. Thus, individuals will be able to take advantage of the benefits that money provides, instead of economising on their holdings of CBDC fearing for higher inflation lowering its return.

In contrast, for agents in the base economy, their utility is strictly decreasing to an increase in π^e , as there is no mechanism for the economy to attain the golden rule. Recall 2.0:

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{1}{1 + \pi^e} = \frac{n}{z}$$

We see the real return of physical money is declining to increase in π^e . As real money holding fall below the optimal level given reduced return, households' consumption pattern will be altered (Champ, Freeman and Haslag, 1994). Agents are forced to reduce consumption when old which requires money to finance and increase consumption when young despite the real utility gained from is lower given diminishing marginal return.

Lastly, for the deposit case, as shown in figure 10, when interest is set to maximise welfare, given exogenous transmission parameter (below $i^* = 2.6\%$), utility of households is decreasing to an increase in π^e . The slope for this decline is increasing to a decrease in μ , or an increase in market power of the commercial bank. This is because for policy makers to retain the return of money across different price level, reserve interest needs to be at $i = \frac{z-1}{\mu}$. At this level, households will be taxed to fund for the interest on reserve, thus failing to satisfy the fiscal optimality condition, resulting in a deposit rate which is not utility maximising for household. Thus, because of the commercial bank holds market power ($\mu < 1$), it is impossible to arrive at an interest rate which both shields return of money from inflation and generate maximum welfare for households.

Results above hold important policy implications. Notably, in both deposit and base case, policy makers have no instrument in the long-term when inflation expectation is adjusting, to retain households' welfare at an equivalent level prior to the inflation shock. This is only possible in the CBDC economy.

However, through holding deposits, agents are more shielded than if they only had access to physical money. The improvement from having deposits and CBDC as a means of payment is increasing as inflation increases.

6 Concluding remarks

Findings of our model rely on the government budget constraint, which in our setup, puts additional tax burden on households when interest becomes high. This sets a ceiling on the level of policy rate, which once exceeded, will result in lower welfare in an economy where physical money is not available as a medium of exchange. Thus, a well-designed, not costly CBDC characterised by low tax, will benefit households.

Compared to an economy with deposits only, our model suggests that when the pass-through between policy and deposit rate is imperfect, introducing a CBDC is desirable, unconditionally. The pareto improvement comes from the improved return on money, and its magnitude becomes greater the more lagged pass-through is. If CBDC co-circulates with deposit, the model predicts for CBDC to crowd out deposits. However, the replacement of CBDC for deposits relies on the fact that our model does not include long-term assets, for which the commercial bank has a comparative advantage.

When CBDC is used as a policy instrument, it enables central banks to retain the real return of money at different price levels, thus shielding the households from inflation by allowing them to make the optimal consumption choices. It also improves efficiency of the policy, as changes in interest rates will prompt agents' behaviour to change, with less adverse impact on utility.

The model does abstract from important real-world considerations. We assume households are indifferent between three types of monies; however, after its pilot in 2020, e-CNY is only used by 1.5% of Chinese citizens and accounts for

0.06% of M0 (PBC, 2021). The cost of accessing (e.g., technical barriers) means that CBDC may have lower convenience value, which would impact transmission of policies. It is important to note that e-CNY is non-interest-bearing, which would lower its attractiveness, compared to an interest-bearing CBDC. However, in the UK, empirical research has shown that household depositors have low price elasticity, such that they often stick to banks (Chiu and Hill, 2015); further work can be done to see at what level, interest on CBDC provides enough of an incentive to encourage switching.

Andolfatto (2020) suggested by having CBDC as a competitive means of payment, commercial banks' market power is reduced (higher μ) which should improve policy pass-through. However, our model shows that improvements in μ which is below a certain threshold is insignificant, and households remain suboptimal compared to the pareto optimal equilibrium achievable if CBDC is accessible as a medium of exchange. Additionally, given the weaker the pass-through is, the greater the improvement in consumer welfare will be through accessing CBDC, we believe there is increasing motivation for planners to introduce CBDC.

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7 Appendix¹⁴

7.1 Appendix A

Rearrange condition 2.7 to find the value of a unit of physical money at period t and $t + 1$:

$$v_t = \frac{N_t(y - c_1)}{M_t}$$
$$v_{t+1} = \frac{N_{t+1}(y - c_1)}{M_{t+1}}$$

Divide the two. Given constant population growth n and constant money supply growth z :

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{\frac{N_{t+1}(y - c_1)}{M_{t+1}}}{\frac{N_t(y - c_1)}{M_t}} = \frac{N_{t+1}M_t}{N_tM_{t+1}} = \frac{n}{z}$$

7.2 Appendix B

Rearrange 2.19 to have m_t as the subject:

$$\frac{(c_2 - T_{t+1})}{(1 + i)v_{t+1}} \leq m_t$$

Substitute back into equation 2.18:

$$c_1 + v_t \frac{(c_2 - T_{t+1})}{(1 + i)v_{t+1}} \leq y$$
$$c_1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{c_2}{1 + i} - \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{T_{t+1}}{1 + i} \leq y$$
$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) \frac{c_2}{1 + i} \leq y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}}\right) \frac{T_{t+1}}{1 + i}$$

Simplify:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1 + i}\right) c_2 \leq y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1 + i}\right) T_{t+1}$$

¹⁴ Note all calculations are step-by-step.

7.3 Appendix C

Part 1. Base case

Market clearing condition and the government budget constraint for the base case economy are respectively given by:

$$N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1}M_{t+1}$$

$$N_t a_{t+1} = (z - 1)v_{t+1}M_t$$

Transform government constraint:

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{\frac{(z-1)v_{t+1}M_{t+1}}{z}}{\frac{N_{t+1}}{n}}$$

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{\frac{n(z-1)}{z}v_{t+1}M_{t+1}}{N_{t+1}}$$

Substitute money market clearing condition, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1}M_{t+1}$:

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{n(z-1)(y - c_1)}{z}$$

Substitute in $q = \frac{1}{1+\frac{n}{z}}\left(\frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n}\right)$:

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{n(z-1)q}{z}$$

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{n(z-1)\left(\frac{1}{1+\frac{n}{z}}\left(\frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n}\right)\right)}{z}$$

Simplify:

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{\frac{n(z-1)}{1+\frac{n}{z}}\left(\frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n}\right)}{z}$$

$$a_{t+1} = \frac{n(z-1)\left(\frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n}\right)}{z+n}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{t+1} &= \frac{(z-1)\left(\frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n}\right)}{\frac{z}{n} + 1} \\
a_{t+1}\frac{\frac{z}{n} + 1}{z-1} &= \frac{n}{z}y - \frac{za_{t+1}}{n} \\
a_{t+1}\frac{\frac{z}{n} + 1}{z-1} + \frac{za_{t+1}}{n} &= \frac{n}{z}y \\
a_{t+1}\left(\frac{n\left(\frac{z}{n} + 1\right) + z(z-1)}{n(z-1)}\right) &= \frac{n}{z}y \\
a_{t+1}\left(\frac{z + n + z^2 - z}{n(z-1)}\right) &= \frac{n}{z}y \\
a_{t+1}\left(\frac{z^2 + n}{n(z-1)}\right) &= \frac{n}{z}y
\end{aligned}$$

At equilibrium where $a_{t+1} = a = a_{t-1}$:

$$a = \frac{n^2(z-1)}{z(z^2+n)}y$$

Thus, we have derived the lump-sum transfer amount in the base case economy dependent on the rate of money expansion.

Part 2. CBDC case

Now, let us find net lump-sum transfer in the CBDC economy, given interest and rate of money expansion. First, the government budget constraint is given by:

$$v_t M_{t-1}(z-1-i) = N_{t-1} T_{t+1}$$

Transform it to next period:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{v_{t+1} M_t}{N_t}(z-1-i) &= T_{t+1} \\
\frac{v_{t+1} M_{t+1}}{\frac{z}{N_{t+1}} \frac{n}{n}}(z-1-i) &= T_{t+1} \\
\frac{nv_{t+1} M_{t+1}}{zN_{t+1}}(z-1-i) &= T_{t+1}
\end{aligned}$$

Substitute money market clearing condition, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1}M_{t+1}$:

$$\frac{n}{z}(y - c_1)(z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\left(\frac{n}{z}q\right)(z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute $q = \frac{1}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i)+1} \left(y \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] - \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1+i)} \right)$:

$$\frac{\frac{n}{z}(z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \left(y \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] - \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1+i)} \right) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] (z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} - \frac{\frac{n}{z}(z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \frac{zT_{t+1}}{n(1+i)} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] (z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} = T_{t+1} + \frac{\frac{n}{z}(z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] (z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} = T_{t+1} \left(1 + \frac{\frac{n}{z}(z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right)} \right)$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] (z - 1 - i)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \frac{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right)}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right) + \frac{n}{z}(z - 1 - i)} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] (z - 1 - i)}{\left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right) + \frac{\frac{n}{z}z - 1 - i}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i)}} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right]}{\frac{\left(\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1 \right)}{z - 1 - i} + \frac{\frac{n}{z}}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i)}} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z} (1+i) \right]}{\left(\frac{n}{z} (1+i) + 1 \right) \frac{1}{z-1-i} + \frac{1}{(1+i)}} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \frac{n}{z} \left[\frac{n}{z} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{\left(\frac{n}{z} (1+i) + 1 \right) (1+i) + (z-1-i)}{(z-1-i)(1+i)}} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \left[\frac{n}{z} (1+i) \right] (z-1-i) \frac{n}{z} (1+i)}{\left(\frac{n}{z} (1+i) + 1 \right) (1+i) + (z-1-i)} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{y \left[\frac{n}{z} (1+i) \right]^2 (z-1-i)}{\left(\frac{n}{z} (1+i) + 1 \right) (1+i) + (z-1-i)} = T_{t+1}$$

At equilibrium where $T_{t+1} = T_{t-1} = T$:

$$\frac{y \left[\frac{n}{z} (1+i) \right]^2 (z-1-i)}{\left(\frac{n}{z} (1+i) + 1 \right) (1+i) + (z-1-i)} = T$$

Thus, we have derived the net lump-sum transfer/tax in the CBDC as the only medium of exchange economy.

7.4 Appendix D

In this appendix, we will first solve for market allocations for base case economy. The unconstrained maximisation for agents is:

$$u(c_1, c_2) = (c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

First-order conditions with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2} (y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0$$

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = (y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

Square both sides:

$$\frac{\left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}q_t + a_{t+1}} = \frac{1}{y - q_t}$$

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}q_t + a_{t+1} = \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2 y - \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2 q_t$$

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}q_t + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2 q_t = \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2 y - a_{t+1}$$

$$q_t \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right) = \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)^2 y - a_{t+1}$$

$$q_t = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} - \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)}$$

$$q_t = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y - \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \right)$$

Solve for c_1 , using budget constraint $c_1 = y - q_t$:

$$c_1 = y - \left[\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} - \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)} \right]$$

$$c_1 = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right) y - \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \left(y + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \right)$$

Solve for c_2 , using budget constraint $c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} q_t + a_{t+1}$:

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left[\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} - \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right)} \right] + a_{t+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} - \frac{a_{t+1}}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + a_{t+1} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + \frac{a_{t+1} \left(1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}\right) - a_{t+1}}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} a_{t+1}}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y}{\frac{v_t + v_{t+1}}{v_t}} + \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_t + v_{t+1}}{v_t}} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t + v_{t+1}} y + \frac{v_{t+1} a_{t+1}}{v_t + v_{t+1}} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{y}{\frac{v_t + v_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}}} + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_t + v_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}}} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \left(\frac{y}{\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} + 1} \right) + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} + 1} \\
c_2 &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} \frac{y}{\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} + 1} + \frac{a_{t+1}}{\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} + 1} \\
c_2 &= \frac{1}{\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} + 1} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} y + a_{t+1} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting in real rate of return of physical money:

$$\begin{aligned}
q_t &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}} \left(\frac{n}{z} y - \frac{z a_{t+1}}{n} \right) \\
c_1 &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}} \left(y + \frac{z a_{t+1}}{n} \right) \\
c_2 &= \frac{1}{\frac{z}{n} + 1} \left(\frac{n}{z} y + a_{t+1} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

7.5 Appendix E

In this appendix, we will solve for market allocations for CBDC economy. The unconstrained maximisation for agents is:

$$u(c_1, c_2) = (c_1)^{\frac{1}{2}} + (c_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

First-order conditions with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2}(y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0$$

Rearrange and solve for q_t :

$$\frac{1}{2}(y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\frac{1}{(y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}{\left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

$$\frac{1}{y - q_t} = \frac{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1}}$$

$$y - q_t = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}$$

$$y - q_t - \frac{q_t}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} = \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}$$

$$y - \frac{q_t \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} = \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}$$

$$y - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2} = \frac{q_t \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}$$

$$q_t \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] = y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}$$

$$q_t = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}$$

$$q_t = \frac{1}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} \left(y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} \right)$$

Solve for c_1 , using budget constraint $c_1 = y - q_t$:

$$c_1 = y - \left\{ \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} \right\}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] - y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{y}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} \left(y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} \right)$$

Solve for c_2 , using budget constraint $c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)q_t + T_{t+1}$:

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \left[\frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} \right] + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} - \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i)} + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right]} + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1} \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right] - T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1 \right]}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1} \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) + 1} \left[y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] + T_{t+1} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}(1+i)}{v_t} \right]}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+i) + v_t}{v_t}} \left[y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] + T_{t+1} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{[v_{t+1}(1+i)]}{v_{t+1}(1+i) + v_t} \left[y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] + T_{t+1} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+i) + v_t}{v_{t+1}(1+i)}} \left[y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] + T_{t+1} \right]$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}(1+i)}} \left[y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right] + T_{t+1} \right]$$

Substituting in real rate of return of digital money $(1+i) \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = (1+i) \frac{n}{z}$:

$$q_t = \frac{1}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \left(y \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i) \right] - \frac{z(T_{t+1})}{n(1+i)} \right)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{\frac{n}{z}(1+i) + 1} \left(y + \frac{z(T_{t+1})}{n(1+i)} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{z}{n(1+i)}} \left[\frac{n}{z}(1+i)y + T_{t+1} \right]$$

7.6 Appendix F

Part 1. Calculation for Lemma 6

Calculate the share of profit for an individual agent when old, given it is split evenly across all old agents:

$$\frac{\Pi_{t+1}}{N_t} = \frac{v_{t+1}d_t N_t(i-r)}{N_t} = v_{t+1}d_t(i-r)$$

Budget constraint when old:

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}(1+r)d_t + T_{t+1} + v_{t+1}d_t(i-r)$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}d_t(1+r+i-r) + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}d_t(1+i) + T_{t+1}$$

Thus, the new budget constraints are:

$$c_1 + v_t d_t \leq y$$

$$c_2 \leq v_{t+1}(1+i)d_t + T_{t+1}$$

Solve for Lifetime budget constraint, rearrange budget constraint when old:

$$\frac{c_2 - T_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}(1+i)} = d_t$$

Substitute back into budget constraint when young:

$$c_1 + v_t \frac{c_2 - T_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}(1+i)} = y$$

$$c_1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{c_2}{1+i} - \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{T_{t+1}}{1+i} = y$$

$$c_1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{c_2}{1+i} = y + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{T_{t+1}}{1+i}$$

Simplify:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+i} \right) T_{t+1}$$

Part 2. Calculation for constructing lifetime budget constraint of deposit case

Rearrange 4.5 to have d_t as the subject:

$$\frac{c_2 - T_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}(1+r)} = d_t$$

Substitute back into equation 4.4:

$$c_1 + v_t \frac{c_2 - T_{t+1}}{v_{t+1}(1+r)} = y$$

$$c_1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{c_2}{1+r} - \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{T_{t+1}}{1+r} = y$$

$$c_1 + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{c_2}{1+r} = y + \frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{T_{t+1}}{1+r}$$

Simplify:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+r} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+r} \right) T_{t+1}$$

Substitute in condition 4.2 which states $\mu i = r$:

$$c_1 + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+\mu i} \right) c_2 = y + \left(\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}} \frac{1}{1+\mu i} \right) T_{t+1}$$

7.7 Appendix G

In this appendix, we will solve for market allocations for deposit economy. The unconstrained maximisation for agents is:

$$\max_{q_t} (y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

First-order conditions with respect to q_t yields:

$$-\frac{1}{2}(y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 0$$

Rearrange and solve for q_t :

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = (y - q_t)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)}{\left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{1}{(y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

$$\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)(y - q_t)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)q_t + T_{t+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Square both side:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+i) \right]^2 (y - q_t) &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) q_t \\ \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 q_t - T_{t+1} &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) q_t \\ \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - T_{t+1} &= \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) q_t + \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 q_t \\ \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - T_{t+1} &= q_t \left\{ \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) + \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 \right\} \\ \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - T_{t+1} &= q_t \left\{ \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) + \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 \right\} \\ \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - T_{t+1} &= q_t \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \left\{ 1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right\} \\ \frac{\left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right]^2 y - T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \left\{ 1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right\}} &= q_t \\ q_t &= \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) y}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \left\{ 1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right\}} \\ q_t &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) y - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Solve for c_1 , using budget constraint $c_1 = y - q_t$:

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= y - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) y - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \right) \\ c_1 &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \left\{ y \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right] - \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) y - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \right) \right\} \\ c_1 &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \left(y \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) \right] - \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r) y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \right) \\ c_1 &= \frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \left(y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Solve for c_2 , using budget constraint $c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)q_t + T_{t+1}$:

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)y - \frac{T_{t+1}}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} \right) \right] + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} - \frac{T_{t+1} \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} + T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} - T_{t+1} \left(\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} - 1 \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} - T_{t+1} \left(\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} - 1 \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} - T_{t+1} \left(\frac{1 - \left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} - T_{t+1} \left(\frac{-\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{y \left[\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]^2}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} + \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} T_{t+1}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left\{ \frac{y \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} \right\}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left\{ \frac{y}{\frac{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} \right\}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \left\{ \frac{y}{\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) + 1} + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[1 + \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t}(1+r) \right]} \right\}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t}}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{1}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} \right]}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t}}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}(1+r)} + 1 \right]}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t}}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} y + \frac{T_{t+1}}{\left[\frac{v_t}{v_{t+1}(1+r)} + 1 \right]}$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{v_{t+1}(1+r)}{v_t} + 1} \left(\frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} (1+r)y + T_{t+1} \right)$$

Substituting in real rate of return of deposit $(1+r) \frac{v_{t+1}}{v_t} = \frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z}$:

$$q_t = q = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z} (1+r)} \left(\frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z} y - \frac{zT_{t+1}}{(1+\mu i)n} \right)$$

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z}} \left(y + \frac{zT_{t+1}}{(1+\mu i)n} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{1}{\frac{z}{(1+\mu i)n} + 1} \left(\frac{(1+\mu i)n}{z} y + T_{t+1} \right)$$

7.8 Appendix H

Now, let us find net lump-sum transfer in the deposit economy, given interest and rate of money expansion. First, the government budget constraint is given by:

$$v_t M_{t-1}(z - 1 - i) = N_{t-1} T_t$$

Transform it to next period:

$$\frac{v_{t+1} M_t}{N_t} (z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{\frac{v_{t+1} M_{t+1}}{z}}{\frac{N_{t+1}}{n}} (z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{nv_{t+1} M_{t+1}}{z N_{t+1}} (z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute money market clearing condition, $N_{t+1}(y - c_1) = v_{t+1} M_{t+1}$:

$$\frac{n}{z} (y - c_1)(z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\left(\frac{n}{z} q\right) (z - 1 - i) = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i) q = T_{t+1}$$

Substitute $q = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{n}{z}(1 + \mu i)} \left[\frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i) y - \frac{z T_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)} \right]$:

$$\frac{\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} \left[\frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i) y - \frac{z T_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)} \right] = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i) y - \frac{\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} \frac{z T_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)} = T_{t+1}$$

$$\frac{\frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i) \frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} y = T_{t+1} + \frac{\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} \frac{z T_{t+1}}{n(1 + \mu i)}$$

$$\frac{\frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i) \frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} y = T_{t+1} \left[1 + \frac{\frac{n}{z} (z - 1 - i)}{1 + \frac{n}{z} (1 + \mu i)} \frac{z}{n(1 + \mu i)} \right]$$